

FORTUNA INDU LANGNA & DHANAYOGAS

O. M. Saravanan* & Dr. V. Kotravel**

* Research Scholar, Department of Astrology, Vels Institute of Science, Technology and Advanced Studies (VISTAS), Pallavaram, Chennai, Tamilnadu

** Research Supervisor, Department of Astrology, Vels Institute of Science, Technology and Advanced Studies (VISTAS), Pallavaram, Chennai, Tamilnadu

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Abstract:

Second bhava is very important for material life. In this earth we all want to live comfortable. Everyman wants to earn money till his death. There are some ways to find out our wealth condition in astrology through fortuna and indu lagna. Dhana yogas point out our wealth status.

Key Words: Second Bhava – Dhana – Family – Promise – Panaparam – Fortuna – Indu – Lagna – Dhana Yogas Maha Yogam – Exchange Yogam – Kala Yogam – Amala Yogam – Lakshmi Yogam – Vibareetha Raja Yogam – Kaja Kesari Yogam – Guru Chandra Yogam – Chandra Mangala Yogam – Vesi Yogam – Vasi Yogam – Ubayasari Yogam – Sunaba Yogam – Anaba Yogam – Thuruthura Yogam – Hamsa Maha Purushayogam – Malavya Maha Prusha Yogam – Sasamaha Purusha Yogam – Athi Yogam – Pancha Maha Yogam – Rusaga Yogam – Pathra Maha Yogam

Introduction:

Money is essential for human life. In astrology Second bhava indicates one's wealth condition. The second bhava is called dhana sthana, vaku (words) sthana, family sthana, nethra(eye) sthana and taste (rushi) sthana. Jupiter is the planet for wealth. The Second bhava lord and Jupiter decide one's wealth. 2/5/8/11 bhavas are called panaparasthana (Dhana kendra). 2/6/10 bhavas are called karma trine. We can calculate one's wealth by seeing the weightage of the above bhavas.

Fortuna (Most Fortune Point):

(Lagna degree + Moon degree) – Sun degree

It is called fortuna point. The fortuna point gives the most fortune to all. Fortuna point stays in lagna at amavasya thithi. It stays in second bhava at thirithyai thithi. It stays in third bhava at panchami thithi. It stays in fourth bhava at saphami thithi. It stays in fifth bhava at navami thithi.

Indu Lagna:

Indu lagna is another fortune point to indicate one's wealth. Mahakavi kalidasar explained in Uthrakalamirtha how to calculate indu lagnam. Planets dimension numbers for Sun – 30, Moon – 16, Mars - 6, Mercury - 8, Jupiter – 10, Venus -12, Saturn -1.

How to Calculate Indu Lagnam?

Indu means moon. First of all we can identify the ninth lord from rasi and lagna. Add both the planets dimension numbers and divide it by 12. Count the balance number from moon, coming rasi is called Indu lagnam. In this house any benefit planets, one should be an crorepathi. Any malefic planets in indu lagna, one should be a lakshathipathi. Money would come in the dasa of the standing planets in indu lagna.

Wealth Related Yogas:

1. Kala Yogam:

Third lord exchange with 1/2/4/5/7/9/10/11 lord, it is called kala yogam. By this yoga the native should do all works fastly and quickly. He will attain all kinds of wealth. Sometimes he speaks good words, sometimes he speaks filthy words. Sometimes he suffers a lot.

2. Maha Yogam:

There are 28 types of Maha yoga. Lagna lord exchanges with 2/4/5 7/9/10/11 lord is total 7 yogas. Similarly second lord exchange with 2/4/5/7/9/10/11th lord is total 7 yogas. Who born with this yoga get blessings from goddesses Lakshmi. They should wear jewels and beautiful dresses. They would receive government rewards and postings. They will get divine child.

Sythanya Yogam:

The sixth / eighth or twelfth lord makes exchange with other planet is called sythanya yogam. They are foolish. They will do sins. They should face troubles from their enemies.

Pancha Maha Yogam:

Mars, Mercury, Jupiter, Venus and Saturn stand in 1/4/7/10th bhava from Moon or Lagna in their own house or exaltation house is called pancha maha yogam. The native who have this yoga is the richest man.

Rusaga Yogam:

Mars should stand in kendras from rasi or lagna, it is called rusaga yogam. They are as equal as the king. They should ever appear youth. They donate well.

Pathra Maha Yogam:

Mercury should stand in kendra from lagna or rasi in its own house or exhaltation house it is called Pathra maha yogam. They should be wealthy and have leadership quality.

Vibareetha Raja Yogam:

Sixth lord stands in eighth or twelveth house, Eighth lord stands in sixth / twelveth house, twelveth lord stands in sixth or eighth house it is called vibareetha rajayogam. The native will get money or power in unexpected way or un expected time.

Lakshmi Yogam:

Nineth lord stands in 1/4/7/10 with exhaltation and aspected by Jupiter / Venus / Mercury it is called lakshmi yogam. The native will be rich.

Kaja Kesari Yogam:

Jupiter stands in 1/4/7/10 house from moon, it is called kaja kesari yogam. It gives name, fame and wealth to one. The meaning of kaja kesari yogam is the elephant is won by the lion, so, this yoga people easily destroy their enemies.

Guru Chandra Yogam:

Moon conjunctions with Jupiter in same house it is called guru chandra yogam. But this combination in 6/8/12th bhava is not good.

Chandra Mangala Yogam:

Moon conjunctions with Mars in same house it is called Chandra mangala yogam. They have lot of lands.

Vasi Yogam:

Any planet except Moon, Rahu and kethu stand twelveth house from Sun, it is called vasi yogam. They are always wealth and have influence in government.

Vesi Yogam:

Any planet except Moon, Rahu and kethu stand second house from Sun, it is called vesi yogam. They are always wealth and have influence in government.

Ubayasari Yogam:

Any planet except Moon, Rahu and kethu stand second and twelveth house from Sun, it is called Ubayasari yogam. They are always wealth and have influence in government.

Sunaba Yogam:

Any planet except Sun stand second house from Moon, it is called Sunba yogam. It gives happiness and comfort in life

Anaba Yogam:

Any planet except Sun stand twelveth house from Moon, it is called Anaba yogam . It gives happiness and comfort in life

Thuruthura yogam:

Any planet except Sun stand second and twelveth house from Moon, it is called Thuruthura yogam . It gives happiness and comfort in life

Hamsa Maha Purusa Yogam:

Jupiter stands in 1/4/7/10 from lagna or rasi with ruling or exhaltation power, it is called hamsa maha purusa yogam. They are wealthy people with generosity.

Malavya Maha Purusha Yogam:

Venus stands in 1/4/7/10 from lagna or rasi with ruling or exhaltation power, it is called Malavya Maha punisha yogam. They are wealthy people with luxurious vehicle.

Sasa Maha Purusha Yogam:

Saturn stands in 1/4/7/10 from lagna or rasi with ruling or exhaltation power, it is called Sasa Maha Purusha yogam. They are wealthy people with sincere labours.

Athi Yogam:

Jupiter, Venus and Mercury stands in 6/7/8 houses from laga or rasi, it is called athi yogam. They are wealthy people.

Conclusion:

Real wealth is health. So, health is wealth. We should give importance to maintain our health. Because, now a days corporate hospitals cheat money from us. A richman is not a rich man. A healthy man is a richman.

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